

How to predict solar energy production

Efficient use of renewable energy sources with machine learning

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Abstract

Solar photovoltaic (PV) energy production is highly dependent on weather, which makes its output difficult to predict. This article presents a practical, data-driven approach to forecasting the daily energy output of a rooftop PV installation in north-eastern Poland, using production data collected through the SolarEdge API together with historical weather data from Meteoblue and computed daylight information. Several forecasting methods are compared — naive and moving-average baselines and Facebook’s Prophet, with and without external weather regressors — and evaluated with standard forecast-accuracy statistics. The results show that adding a small number of readily available weather variables lets Prophet predict PV output with satisfactory accuracy and anticipate sudden changes in production.

Keywords: solar energy, PV forecasting, Prophet, time series, machine learning, weather data

Solar power systems could be a key tool for energy production for the present and future generations. Solar energy is environmentally friendly and provides electricity to places where it is difficult to build conventional infrastructure. Photovoltaic (PV) cells become cheaper each year. Solar energy is cheaper than ever.

However, it has two huge obstacles: energy is produced only during the daytime and the amount of energy produced is highly dependent on the weather. Machine learning algorithms combined with weather data have the potential to overcome these barriers, which results with more efficient use of renewable energy sources.

In this article, you will learn about predicting time series depending on external (weather) conditions. I will show you how to improve your predictions using the domain knowledge of the target variable. We will go quickly through collecting data about energy production

Figure 1: The average cost of solar panels has fallen 65% from \$7.34 per watt in 2010, to \$2.53 per watt in 2019. (source: HomeGuide, <https://homeguide.com/costs/solar-panel-cost#kwh>)

from the solar farm through its producers API. Next, we will analyze gathered data and select features for time-series forecasting. Finally, we will train and test several predictive models and identify the best, most suitable for the described case.

1 Why?

The problem with setting up solar power sources is that it is difficult to predict how much power it will generate once it's built. Of course, we can quite accurately calculate the amount of solar energy reaching the Earth's surface under ideal weather conditions¹. However, weather fluctuations and the unique microclimate of each location affect current energy production by renewable energy installations. This forces scheduling of tasks that require a lot of power.

To maximize the environmental and financial benefits of using renewable energy, we need to alter our habits. Making the electricity system intelligent and flexible will help optimize our behaviour and manage household energy consumption. Energy-consuming tasks can be scheduled for days or even hours of best weather conditions.

Lastly, knowing your system's production tells you how quickly your solar system will return the investment.

¹<https://www.pveducation.org/pvc/drom/properties-of-sunlight/calculation-of-solar-insolation>

2 Device

My friends have PV cells for more than a year.

Figure 2: Czaplisko Siedlisko is a guesthouse located at the shore of Jeziorak lake, among forest and meadows. Bird's songs will accompany you every day. Modern stud wall house with 1.5 hectares of land at your disposal — our proposal of an unforgettable vacation! (<https://czapliskosiedlisko.pl/>)

The whole installation has 31 panels that occupy 53 square metres of the roof. Inverter manages electricity generation. It is a device that converts direct current (produced by PV cells) into alternating current (used by household appliances), and manages the entire installation. Unused surplus is fed into the public electricity grid, which reduces the owner's electricity bill.

The inverter is manufactured by Solar Edge, which has equipped it with internet connectivity. The device sends statistics about energy production to the company, who makes it available to the owner of the installation via a mobile application, a website and API.

3 Acknowledgements

Special thanks are going to Czaplisko Siedlisko² for sharing data from their solar farm.

Also, thanks Meteoblue³ for providing historical weather data for the location of the panels.

4 Data collecting

All code and data used in this article are available here: Solar Energy Forecasting in north-eastern Poland⁴.

First, we need to collect and store data from SolarEdge API.

```
{
  "energy": {
    "timeUnit": "DAY",
    "unit": "Wh",
    "measuredBy": "INVERTER",
    "values": [
```

²Editorial correction, 2026: the original link <https://en.czapliskosiedlisko.pl/> no longer resolves; updated to the working domain. <https://czapliskosiedlisko.pl/>

³<https://www.meteoblue.com/>

⁴Editorial correction, 2026: the original repository <https://github.com/fischerbach/fischerbach.github.io/tree/master/sol> is no longer available (the author's former GitHub account was removed). The notebook and data samples are archived with this Zenodo deposit. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20562980>

```

        {
            "date": "2020-12-09 00:00:00",
            "value": 2911.0
        }
    ]
}
}

```

A typical response to an API request

To avoid repetition in the code, I sketched a simple API client.

```

class SolarEdgeClient:
    def __init__(self, key):
        self.key = key

    def show_key(self):
        print(self.key)

    def getDataPeriod(self, site_id):
        url = f"https://monitoringapi.solaredge.com/site/{site_id}/dataPeriod?api_key={self.key}"
        response = requests.request("GET", url, headers={}, data = {})
        data = response.json()
        return (data['dataPeriod']['startDate'], data['dataPeriod']['endDate'])

    def getSiteEnergy(self, site_id, start_date, end_date, time_unit='DAY'):
        url = f"https://monitoringapi.solaredge.com/site/{site_id}/energy?timeUnit={time_unit}&endDate={end_date}&startDate={start_date}&api_key={self.key}"
        response = requests.request("GET", url, headers={}, data = {})
        data = response.json()

        return data['energy']['values']

    def getSiteDetails(self, site_id):
        url = f"https://monitoringapi.solaredge.com/site/{site_id}/details?api_key={self.key}"
        response = requests.request("GET", url, headers={}, data = {})
        data = response.json()

        return data['details']

    def read_site_energy(self, site_id, start_date, end_date, time_unit='DAY'):
        site_details = self.getSiteDetails(site_id)
        datelist = pd.date_range(start_date, end=end_date).tolist()

```

```

energyData = pd.DataFrame()
for date in datelist:
    dailyData = self.getSiteEnergy(site_id=site_id,
    ↪ start_date=date.strftime("%Y-%m-%d"), end_date=date.strftime("%Y-%m-%d"),
    ↪ time_unit=time_unit)
    temporary_df = pd.DataFrame.from_records(dailyData)
    if(time_unit != 'DAY'):
        temporary_df['date'] = temporary_df['date'].apply(lambda date:
    ↪ Helpers.localtime_to_utc(date, site_details['location']['timeZone']))
        energyData = pd.concat([energyData, temporary_df])
return energyData

```

It is worth noting that if you are dealing with time-series data, especially in hour or greater frequencies, you must take care of the time zones of all data sources. I recommend you convert datetimes to UTC timezone or to UNIX timestamps as soon as you import a timezone-aware dataset. For this purpose, I wrote some helper functions, which I have collected in one class as static functions. This makes the code more readable, without the risk of functions' name conflict.

```

from astral.sun import sun
from astral.sun import daylight
from astral import LocationInfo

class Helpers:
    @staticmethod
    def localtime_to_utc(date, local_timezone="Europe/Warsaw"):
        local = pytz.timezone(local_timezone)
        naive = datetime.datetime.strptime (date, "%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
        local_dt = local.localize(naive, is_dst=True)
        utc_dt = local_dt.astimezone(pytz.utc)
        return utc_dt.strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")

    @staticmethod
    def generate_daylight(start_date, end_date):
        datelist = pd.date_range(start_date, end=end_date).tolist()
        daylightData = pd.DataFrame(columns=['date', 'daylight', 'sunrise', 'sunset'])
        for date in datelist:
            daylight = Helpers.getDaylight(date)
            daylightData = daylightData.append({
                "date": date,
                "daylight": daylight['duration'],
                "sunrise": daylight['sunrise'],
                "sunset": daylight['sunset']
            }, ignore_index=True)
        return daylightData

```

```

@staticmethod
def getDaylight(start_date, timezone="Europe/Warsaw"):
    city = LocationInfo("Skitlawki", "Poland", timezone, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE)
    s = sun(city.observer, date=start_date)
    return {
        "duration": (s['sunset'] - s['sunrise']).seconds,
        "sunrise": s['sunrise'].strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S"),
        "sunset": s['sunset'].strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
    }

```

5 We look at the data and establish success indicators

The first step to develop a predictive model for specific time series is to identify and understand the underlying pattern of the data over time. Data collected in the previous section contains the electricity output of the solar PV system, which is measured in kilowatt-hours (kWh). Just like in a smartphone's battery, the kilowatt-hours unit describes how much energy is produced and can be used to power household appliances. 1 kilowatt-hour corresponds to the amount of energy consumed per hour by a 1,000-watt device.

date	value
2020-03-05	13895.0
2020-03-06	3245.0
2020-03-07	32336.0
2020-03-08	4228.0
2020-03-09	26802.0
2020-03-10	28464.0
2020-03-11	8922.0
2020-03-12	29895.0

Full data: *energy_daily_sample.csv*⁵

Another metric is the current power production (measured in kilowatts), which describes how much power at the specific moment a solar panel can provide. For example, if the PV cells produce 1000 W at a specific moment, it is theoretically possible to supply two devices with the requirement of 450 W each and 100W remains. But to power, a 2500 W milling machine may require additional power to be obtained from the public grid.

After consulting the receivers of my forecasts, we have established that the information about the daily expected number of kilowatt-hours will be most valuable to them. The actual home

⁵Editorial correction, 2026: the original gist is no longer available; the file *energy_daily_sample.csv* is archived with this Zenodo deposit. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20562980>

equipment does not require sophisticated energy flow management techniques, so the moment the power of the system will not apply in the foreseeable future. In the following, we will therefore focus on the total energy produced (or to be produced) on a given day. The forecast horizon will be 5 days.

Figure 3: Not surprisingly, it shows an annual fluctuation that is tied to the seasons. *Unless stated otherwise, all pictures in the article are by the author.*

6 Simple forecasts

Before we will go deeper into forecasting based on external variables, let’s try to make a prediction having historical values of the target variable — daily electricity amounts produced by PV cells.

Naive forecast. This is a very basic method in which the predicted value is simply the value of the most recent observation. In our case, it will be energy produced the day before the prediction date.

Moving average. Another basic forecasting method is moving average. Moving average is rather a technical tool to analyse the time series, however, is extremely useful for forecasting long-term trends. In this case, we will use a simple moving average, which is a calculation that takes an arithmetic mean of a specific number of days in the past.

Code below tests those methods.

```

data = energy.copy()
data['cap'] = data['y'].max()
data['floor'] = 0.0
simple_methods = []
### Naive
MODEL = 'Naive'
data[MODEL] = data['y'].shift(periods=1)
arg = (data[MODEL], data['y'])
simple_methods.append([MODEL, *FES.all(*arg)])

### Moving Average
MODEL = 'Moving Average'
data[MODEL] = data['y'].rolling(4).mean().shift(periods=1)
arg = (data[MODEL], data['y'])
simple_methods.append([MODEL, *FES.all(*arg)])

simple_methods_df = pd.DataFrame(simple_methods, columns= ['Method', 'ME', 'MSE',
↪ 'RMSE', 'MAE', 'MPE', 'MAPE', 'U1', 'U2'])
display(simple_methods_df.set_index('Method'))
simple_methods_df.to_html('naive_and_moving_average.html', index=False)

plot_data = data['2020-06':'2020-07']
fig = plt.figure(figsize=(40,14))
plt.xlabel('date',fontsize=40, labelpad=25)
plt.ylabel('energy [Wh]',fontsize=40, labelpad=25)
plt.plot(plot_data['y'], linewidth=2.5)
plt.plot(plot_data['Naive'], linewidth=0.75)
plt.plot(plot_data['Moving Average'], linewidth=0.75)
plt.legend(['Real value', 'Naive', 'Moving Average'], prop={'size': 20})
plt.title('Naive and moving average',fontsize=40, pad=30)

# plt.show()
plt.savefig('naive_and_moving_average.png')

```

Note: We haven't split the dataset for training and test sets yet. By definition of those methods, there is no risk of using data from the future.

7 How to evaluate forecasts (1)

Now, for both methods, we should calculate several forecast evaluation statistics.

If you want to know more about forecast evaluation statistics, please read my article:

Forecast evaluation statistics with examples in Python⁶

⁶<https://fischerbach.medium.com/forecast-evaluation-statistics-with-examples-in-python-6b540ef751c2>

The table below shows the results of the evaluation:

Method	ME	MSE	RMSE	MAE	MPE	MAPE	U ₁	U ₂
Naive	-54.236797	2.680684e+08	16372.794929	12030.301533	-70.256634	110.476107	0.231814	1.000000
Moving Average	-110.428082	1.872068e+08	13682.351887	10319.265411	-85.586637	114.250961	0.197774	0.876008

As expected, these methods are not very accurate. We will use those as a benchmark to evaluate more sophisticated ones. Because, if a more complicated model is less accurate than those forecasts, then there is something wrong. The main indicator of success is the ability of the model to inform about sudden changes in values of time series. No matter how well the trend fits the data, it can't inform in time of sudden changes in production volume (because those are induced by external conditions).

In this context, to achieve our goal, we need a more advanced solution.

8 We need the Prophet

Our second shot will be Prophet⁷ library from Facebook. The Prophet is a procedure for forecasting time series data based on an additive model where non-linear trends are fit with yearly, weekly, and daily seasonality, plus holiday effects.

Creators of the Prophet advertise it as giving a reasonable forecast on messy data with no manual effort.

So, let's test this declaration.

```
from fbprophet import Prophet
from fbprophet.plot import add_changepoints_to_plot
from fbprophet.diagnostics import cross_validation

# (...)

def prophet_without_regressors(train, test):
    m = Prophet(daily_seasonality=False, weekly_seasonality=False,
↪ yearly_seasonality=True, growth='logistic')
    m.fit(train)
    forecast = m.predict(test)
    forecast['yhat'] = forecast['yhat'].apply(lambda x: 0 if x<0 else x)
    return forecast.set_index('ds')['yhat']
```

9 How to evaluate forecast (2)

For the reliability of forecasts, the model can't be trained using future data.

⁷<https://facebook.github.io/prophet/>

Therefore, for further evaluation and comparison of forecasts, we will use training and test sets. The size of the training set is typically about 20% of the total sample, depending on how large is the sample and the forecasting horizon. Since we have more than a year's data and, also, the forecast is only to cover the next few days, we can use a more sophisticated method. Instead of splitting the whole sample once, there are a series of training and test sets, separated from the sample as shown below.

Each training set is used for the creation of a new model and then we calculate evaluation statistics using the corresponding test set.

```
def cross_validation(data, model=prophet_without_regressors):
    date_range = (data['ds'].min()+datetime.timedelta(days=365), data['ds'].max())
    datelist = pd.date_range(*date_range, freq='5D').tolist()
    evaluation_statistics = []
    for i in range(len(datelist)):
        if (i == len(datelist) - 1):
            continue
        train_end = datelist[i]
        test_start = datelist[i] + datetime.timedelta(days=1)
        test_end = test_start + datetime.timedelta(days=5)
        if(test_end > data['ds'].max()):
            test_end = data['ds'].max()
    else:
```

```

test_end = datelist[i] + datetime.timedelta(days=5)
train_end = datetime.datetime.strptime(train_end, '%Y-%m-%d')
test_start = datetime.datetime.strptime(test_start, '%Y-%m-%d')
test_end = datetime.datetime.strptime(test_end, '%Y-%m-%d')

train = data[:train_end].copy()
test = data[test_start:test_end].copy()
train['ds'] = train.index
test['ds'] = test.index

evaluation_statistics.append([f":{train_end} | {test_start} -
↪ {test_end}", *FES.all(model(train, test), test['y'])])
evaluation_statistics = pd.DataFrame(evaluation_statistics, columns=
↪ ['period', 'ME', 'MSE', 'RMSE', 'MAE', 'MPE', 'MAPE', 'U1', 'U2'])
return evaluation_statistics
    
```

It reproduces the real way of evaluating the forecast, as forecasts will be converted once every 5 days.

Method	ME	MSE	RMSE	MAE	MPE	MAPE	U ₁	U ₂
Moving Average	-581.856977	2.064222e+08	13109.980501	10977.422093	-60.078129	85.785519	0.245735	0.865015
Prophet without regressors	-1300.862027	2.355665e+08	13746.089570	11722.623883	-37.836540	72.043319	0.272606	0.928225

The Prophet is not doing better than the moving average. By the nature of the problem, it cannot take full advantage of the possibility of matching seasonality (after all, sunlight does not show weekly or monthly seasonality). MAPE for Prophet is slightly lower than for moving average. This suggests that it reacts to trend changes a little faster. Another statistic — Their’s U₂ is less than 1, so both models are doing better than naive.

However, after a visual inspection of the chart of Prophet’s forecasts, it is encouraging to add external variables.

10 What are the factors that affect solar panels' efficiency?

10.1 Theory

The kilowatt-hour production of a solar system depends on how much sunlight hits the panels and for how long. (source)⁸

The amount of available sunlight depends on the local solar resource, weather conditions, panel orientation, amount of shading, system design and type of mounting (ground or roof mount).

Every installation is different. Things like the angle of PV, wiring and location-specific weather conditions could lead to short-term variability in results.

10.2 Location

Different parts of Earth's surface receive different amounts of sunlight.

Figure 4: Most of the data were obtained for the exact location of the solar farm.

10.3 Weather conditions

Variables that may have a physical impact on the production of electricity by PV cells:

- air temperature,
- precipitation,
- snowfall,

⁸Editorial correction, 2026: the original page <https://www.solarunitedneighbors.org/news/predict-solar-output-production-2/> is no longer available; linked to the Internet Archive snapshot. <http://web.archive.org/web/20240619041327/https://www.solarunitedneighbors.org/news/predict-solar-output-production-2/>

- relative humidity,
- cloud cover,
- sunshine duration,
- solar radiation.

Figure 5: It is easy to see that a larger cloud cover reduces the efficiency of solar panels.

Cloud coverage does not mean that no sunlight will reach solar panels, but the amount will be reduced.⁹ Moreover, PV cells are often installed on the roofs of high buildings. Because of the lack of availability of reliable forecasts for every variable, not all of them will be used in the final model.

The approach proposed in this article is customizable for all installations and is independent of any device-specific characteristics (such as declared efficiency of PV cells). Also, the side goal is to use regressors easily accessible in most weather forecast services.

10.4 Temperature

Interestingly, air temperature is important not because it correlates with sun activity only. The efficiency of the PV cell depends on its temperature, which increases when the temperature drops and decreases when the temperature rises.

11 Weather dataset

As you know from previous sections, reliable weather data is crucial to the short- and long-term prediction of energy production. We should distinguish between two types of weather data: historical (from real-world measurements) and forecasted.

⁹Editorial note, 2026: in the original article this figure was an animation; a single representative frame is reproduced here. The animated version (energy_vs_weather_animated.gif) is included in the accompanying Zenodo deposit.

Just like in our future solar energy model, the weather forecast is also modelled. When creating models you should always focus on the domain of the problem and decide whether the model should be trained using historical weather forecasts or rather using past real measurements.

Figure 6: Typical weather forecast (source: Meteoblue)

For example, if you have to predict the purchase of tickets to an amusement park, you better take into account the weather forecast, because consumers often consider it when they are planning such activities. The advantage of this approach is also that (assuming the stability of the weather forecast error itself) the weather forecast error will have an easier predictable impact on the final predictions.

On the other hand, if you are to predict the results of physical quantity measurements, it will be better to take into account real measurements of past predictors. Then the resultant forecast error will have a more difficult to analyse random distribution (resulting from interferences between the resultant model and weather forecast model). But, at the same time, the model will be resistant to changes in weather modelling.

In the solution described in this article, I used historical data for the weather, because available sunlight is variable depending on real physical conditions. Unfortunately, there are no weather stations near the location of the solar panels. But simulation data could be a good compromise.

12 Meteoblue

Courtesy of Meteoblue¹⁰, I was given access to historical weather data for the location of the solar panels. Their product history+¹¹ offers consistent weather simulation data in hourly resolution since 1985. Higher-resolution data are available since 2008 for nearly every place on Earth. Meteoblue history+ is a paid service, but you can test it for free with full historical data for Basel, Switzerland. For other locations, data is limited to the last 2 weeks.

Figure 7: Available variables (screenshot from meteoblue.com)

The data has been downloaded into a CSV file and requires minor processing.

13 Daylight

There is one other data source that I have used. Day length for every location on Earth changes during the year, with an average of 12 hours of light.

We should generate the length of each day of the year and the times of sunrises and sunsets. They will be needed later to resample the weather data.

```

from astral.sun import sun
from astral.sun import daylight
from astral import LocationInfo

class Helpers:
    @staticmethod
    def localtime_to_utc(date, local_timezone="Europe/Warsaw"):
        local = pytz.timezone(local_timezone)
        naive = datetime.datetime.strptime (date, "%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
    
```

¹⁰<https://www.meteoblue.com/>

¹¹<https://www.meteoblue.com/en/historyplus>

Figure 8: It is easy to see that the solar energy produced is dependent on the length of the day.

```

local_dt = local.localize(naive, is_dst=True)
utc_dt = local_dt.astimezone(pytz.utc)
return utc_dt.strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")

@staticmethod
def generate_daylight(start_date, end_date):
    datelist = pd.date_range(start_date, end=end_date).tolist()
    daylightData = pd.DataFrame(columns=['date', 'daylight', 'sunrise', 'sunset'])
    for date in datelist:
        daylight = Helpers.getDaylight(date)
        daylightData = daylightData.append({
            "date": date,
            "daylight": daylight['duration'],
            "sunrise": daylight['sunrise'],
            "sunset": daylight['sunset']
        }, ignore_index=True)
    return daylightData

@staticmethod
def getDaylight(start_date, timezone="Europe/Warsaw"):
    city = LocationInfo("Skitlawki", "Poland", timezone, LATITUDE, LONGITUDE)
    s = sun(city.observer, date=start_date)
    return {
        "duration": (s['sunset'] - s['sunrise']).seconds,
        "sunrise": s['sunrise'].strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S"),
        "sunset": s['sunset'].strftime ("%Y-%m-%d %H:%M:%S")
    }

```

14 Collecting all data for the final set

Let's gather all data (energy, weather and daylight) in one DataFrame.

```
dataset = pd.merge(left=meteoblue, right=daylight)
dataset['sunrise'] = pd.to_datetime(dataset['sunrise'])
dataset['sunset'] = pd.to_datetime(dataset['sunset'])
dataset['is_day'] = dataset[['ds', 'sunrise', 'sunset']].apply(lambda x: x['sunrise'] <=
↪ x['ds'] <= x['sunset'], axis=1)
display(dataset.head())

df = dataset.loc[dataset['is_day']].drop('is_day', axis=1)

aggregations_dict = {
    'Temperature [2 m elevation corrected]': 'mean',
    'Temperature [1000 mb]': 'mean',
    'Temperature [850 mb]': 'mean',
    'Temperature [700 mb]': 'mean',
    'Precipitation Total': 'sum',
    'Snowfall Amount': 'sum',
    'Relative Humidity [2 m]': 'mean',
    # (...)
    'Temperature': 'mean',
    'Soil Temperature [0-10 cm down]': 'mean',
    'Soil Moisture [0-10 cm down]': 'mean',
    'Vapor Pressure Deficit [2 m]': 'mean',
    'daylight': 'mean',
}

for key in aggregations_dict.keys():
    df[key] = pd.to_numeric(df[key])

df = df.resample('D', on='ds').agg(aggregations_dict).reset_index()
df = pd.merge(left=data.drop('ds', axis=1).drop(['cap', 'floor'], axis=1), right=df,
↪ left_on='ds', right_on='ds')
```

The resulting set has 46 columns, so a sample is shown here as raw CSV (full file: final_dataset_sample.csv)¹²:

```
ds,y,Temperature [2 m elevation corrected],Temperature [1000 mb],Temperature [850
↪ mb],Temperature [700 mb],Precipitation Total,Snowfall Amount,Relative Humidity [2
↪ m],Wind Speed [10 m],Wind Direction [10 m],Wind Speed [80 m],Wind Direction [80
↪ m],Wind Gust,Wind Speed [900 mb],Wind Direction [900 mb],Wind Speed [850 mb],Wind
↪ Direction [850 mb],Wind Speed [700 mb],Wind Direction [700 mb],Wind Speed [500
↪ mb],Wind Direction [500 mb],Cloud Cover Total,Cloud Cover High [high cld lay],Cloud
↪ Cover Medium [mid cld lay],Cloud Cover Low [low cld lay],CAPE [180-0 mb above
↪ gnd],Sunshine Duration,Shortwave Radiation,Direct Shortwave Radiation,Diffuse
↪ Shortwave Radiation,Mean Sea Level Pressure [MSL],Geopotential Height [1000
↪ mb],Geopotential Height [850 mb],Geopotential Height [700 mb],Geopotential Height
↪ [500 mb],Evapotranspiration,FAO Reference Evapotranspiration [2 m],Temperature,Soil
↪ Temperature [0-10 cm down],Soil Moisture [0-10 cm down],Vapor Pressure Deficit [2
```

¹²Editorial correction, 2026: the original gist is no longer available; the file final_dataset_sample.csv is archived with this Zenodo deposit. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20562980>

```
2019-05-09,32425.0,12.64,12.65,2.47,-5.80,0.30,0.0,54.31,...,56060,2019-05-
↪ 09,71061.0,0.0
2019-05-10,32269.0,13.85,13.60,2.99,-5.70,0.20,0.0,72.25,...,56276,2019-05-
↪ 10,71061.0,0.0
```

Final dataset

15 Forecasting

To select external variables from a previously prepared dataset, we focus on two characteristics. First is the physical influence of variables, such as temperature and solar power reaching PV cells' surface. Second is the correlation with the target variable. As we cannot be sure that some weather-related variable isn't correlated somehow with another, which is directly tied with the effectiveness of solar farm, but unavailable to measure directly.

```
correlation_table = df.corr()
target_correlation_table = correlation_table.loc[correlation_table.index ==
↪ 'y'].transpose()

regressors = target_correlation_table.loc[np.abs(target_correlation_table['y']) >=
↪ 0.1].index.values
display(regressors)
```

The method of selecting variables was straightforward. First, we should reject variables with a close to zero correlation with the target variable. Let's see how the model is doing with the remaining variables.

```
def prophet_with_regressors(train, test):
    m = Prophet(daily_seasonality=False, weekly_seasonality=False,
↪ yearly_seasonality=True, growth='logistic')
    for col in train.columns:
        if col in regressors and col not in ['y', 'cap', 'floor', 'Naive', 'Moving
↪ Average']:
            m.add_regressor(col)

    m.fit(train)

    forecast = m.predict(test)
    forecast['yhat'] = forecast['yhat'].apply(lambda x: 0 if x<0 else x)

    return forecast.rename(columns={'yhat': 'y'}).set_index('ds')['y']
```

Model	ME	MSE	RMSE	MAE	MPE	MAPE	U ₁	U ₂
Moving Average	-581.856977	2.064222e+08	13109.980501	10977.422093	-60.078129	85.785519	0.245735	0.865015
Prophet without regressors	-1300.862027	2.355665e+08	13746.089570	11722.623883	-37.836540	72.043319	0.272606	0.928225
Prophet with regressors #1	-1048.635098	8.566480e+07	8352.222840	7057.735309	-26.965930	53.955489	0.166595	0.671991

Quite a good one. Not only does the model have the best statistics so far, but it is also able to inform in advance about sudden changes in production values. The MSE is an order of magnitude smaller than previous attempts!

16 Limiting the number of necessary regressors

Variables such as Shortwave Radiation are obviously linked to solar electricity production, but at the same time are not easily accessible in the weather forecast. Therefore, we will now try to limit the number of variables to the necessary minimum and to those that can be found in any weather forecast.

	ME	MSE	RMSE	MAE	MPE	MAPE	U ₁	U ₂
Moving Average	-581.856977	2.064222e+08	13109.980501	10977.422093	-60.078129	85.785519	0.245735	0.865015
Prophet without regressors	-1300.862027	2.355665e+08	13746.089570	11722.623883	-37.836540	72.043319	0.272606	0.928225
Prophet with regressors	-1048.635098	8.566480e+07	8352.222840	7057.735309	-26.965930	53.955489	0.166595	0.671991
Prophet with fewer regressors	-776.823059	1.021681e+08	9178.062756	7837.312512	-22.487062	58.635851	0.193207	0.737731

Quite close to the 'full' model.

17 Conclusions

With the use of a relatively small number of weather variables, electricity production by PV cells can be predicted with satisfactory accuracy. Importantly, the predictions of explanatory variables are easily accessible in most weather forecasts. However, if we use all measurable variables, the model achieves correspondingly better results.

18 Future directions

Predictive models, aware of how prices, supply and demand are shaped and knowing future forecasts of energy production, can prepare recommendations for owners as to their behaviour on the energy market. This can create additional revenue opportunities for users of renewable energy sources.

My friends have a smart home solution. They already integrate their lights in it and schedule dishwasher or washing machine cycles with potential high PV activity. In the future, all of their power plugs could be scheduled by solar prediction. Another direction is to provide the forecasts in the form of a kitchen dashboard.

19 References

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- http://www.geo.mtu.edu/KeweenawGeoheritage/MiTEP_ESI-2/Solar_energy_and_latitude.html
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